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Education for Sustainable Development: Faculty Perspectives, Curricular Integration, and Institutional Challenges in Higher Education

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Abstract

Sustainable Development (ESD) is now an international demand for higher education institutions to be aligned with SDG 4.7. It aims to prepare students with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to foster sustainable development. The study was qualitative study with phenomenological research design. 10 faculty members from a public university of Punjab were selected through purposive sampling technique. Data collection was done through semi-structured interviews. To analyze the semi-structured interviews data, thematic analysis technique was used. According to the results, there is diversity among faculty members. In conceptual knowledge, most of the participants restrict ESD to environmental awareness, while others take a more socio-ethical approach. There

is not comprehensive integration of the curriculum and sustainability issues are only rarely mentioned, being extremely dependent on individual initiatives rather than institutional. Some major challenges include outdated curricula, ineffective management, and insufficient funding. The analysis concludes that Pakistani universities are at the stage of learning to sustain, having developed awareness, but now need to concentrate on sustaining this learning through systematic curriculum reform, capacity building, and institutional collaboration. It is recommended that university policies be aligned with SDG 4.7, sustainability competencies be integrated throughout programs, faculty and students be empowered, sustainability offices be established, and partnerships be built to facilitate collective action.

Keywords: Education for Sustainable Development, Sustainability, SDG 4.7, Curriculum Integration, Higher Education, Faculty Development.

Introduction

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) has become a core focus of 21st century higher education and is strengthened by the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Long, 2019). In the view of Laurie et al. (2016), in education there is a great significance to sustainability for a sustainable future. Target 4.7 of SDG 4 requires that all learners acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to enhance sustainable development through education that promotes sustainable development, sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, and

global citizenship. The ESD 2030 framework created by UNESCO may help to create a more equitable and sustainable world by enhancing ESD and helping to accomplish all 17 SDGs. It is therefore the challenge of universities around the world to develop graduates capable of becoming sustainability change agents in any field, and not just in the traditional environmental area.

ESD has evolved into a competence-based, transformative philosophy. In a Delphi study, an international panel of 14 experts narrowed down the base of primary sustainability competencies and suggested values-thinking competency as an underpinning competency with intrapersonal and implementation competencies that ought to infuse all higher education learning practices (Brundiers et al., 2021). Such competencies are systems thinking, proactive thinking, regulating competence, strategic competence, interpersonal competence, intrapersonal competence, implementation competence, and integration competence. According to this framework, curricula and pedagogy will have to be restructured so that graduates are not only generally literate but also transformative skilled, able to think in prospective terms and respond to interdependent sustainability problems.

UNESCO (2017) has advocated ESD, that is, transformational learning process where students are equipped with skills on the way to make informed choices and take responsible actions to benefit the environment, economically viable society and the just society, today and in future, respecting cultural differences. ESD is designed to become transdisciplinary and transformative and can be included in curricula, assessments, teaching methodology and learning environments that promote critical thinking, problem-solving abilities and acting capacity to solve sustainability problems (Lavrinoviča, 2021). The importance of critical thinking has been emphasized in some of the previous studies on the national level in terms of perception of teachers (Jamil et al., 2023), practice of teachers (Jamil and Muhammad, 2019), integration of policy documents (Jamil et al., 2020), in textbooks (Jamil et al., 2025; Jamil et al., 2024).

UNESCO is advising governments to apply the ESD 2030 framework and organize resources at the national level. This momentum is experienced globally, although its implementation is not uniform. Although sustainability modules are being integrated into various disciplines in many institutions, most efforts are incremental rather than systemic (UNESCO, 2017).

The global ESD discourse has established itself in the policy discourse of the higher education sector in Pakistan, although it has been implemented on individually basis (Khushik & Diemer, 2018). SDG 4.7 and sustainability are increasingly being mentioned in the strategic plans of universities, but there is still little coordinated action. The main problems are poor governance, insufficient funding, a lack of trained faculty, and outdated curricula, which hinder sustainability exploration (Shah, 2025). Nevertheless, there are areas of progress that indicate what can be achieved when there is blending between intentional program design and institutional commitment. This study thus explores the understanding of ESD, the experiences and implementation of ESD in public universities of Punjab, Pakistan and examines the opportunities and challenges on the way to attaining sustainable higher education.

Objectives of the Study:

To explore faculty perspectives of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) at university level

To examine the integration of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) within university curricula, teaching practices, and institutional structures.

To explore challenges affecting implementation of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) in higher education

Literature Review

The UNESCO ESD 2030 plan has five areas of priority action designed to assist member states in realizing the SDGs: policy, learning environment, educational capacity, youth engagement, and community action (Long, 2019). Its main goals encompass the complete integration of ESD and the 17 SDGs into policy, learning, and teaching settings, as well as teachers' competence building, youth empowerment, and sustainable development at the local level. This is the global agenda that urges universities to integrate sustainability into their curricula, operations, research, and outreach rather than viewing it as additional content.

The history of ESD demonstrates a shift from environmental awareness to competency-oriented change. Scholars were able to define eight major sustainability competencies through a Delphi study involving international experts, encompassing systems thinking, anticipatory, normative, strategic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, implementation, and integration competencies (Brundiens et al., 2021). These competencies provide an outline for producing graduates who can address interdependent sustainability problems through transformative action, rather than focusing on a single learning outcome.

Pakistan is a signatory state to the SDGs, and it has incorporated ESD in its national education policy. The National Education Policy (2017) is explicit on the role of ESD in enhancing quality of life (NEP, 2017), and the Higher Education Commission has been publishing green campus guidelines since 2018. There is a guarantee of free and compulsory education in Article 25-A of the constitution of Pakistan.

However, there is a serious issue of implementation. The education system of Pakistan is upset by historical marginalization, inefficiencies within the education sector, poor funding, curriculum-related challenges, faculty shortage, poor infrastructure, and access to modern learning facilities (Shah, 2025). Although policy is acknowledged, implementation is never uniform due to a lack of teacher readiness, underdeveloped policy facilities, and inadequate resources. The first announcement by the government to reduce its higher education budget in 2024-25 in the fiscal year created ripples in the academic world, which brought out the unstable Pakistani education funding position.

A systematic review of 26 studies on higher education in Pakistan revealed that sustainability efforts were present in campus management and certain outreach programs; however, there is no evidence of sustainability efforts in fundamental aspects such as curriculum, research, and faculty development (Hinduja et al., 2023). A study on technology education in Pakistan revealed that 71 percent of students were unaware of sustainability in their disciplines (Malik et al., 2019). In comparison, only 17 percent of all students understood the basic definitions of sustainability and 12 percent had some familiarity with sustainability as a field related to technology education. Surveys indicate that there is a lack of sustainability in all the spheres of higher learning institutions in Pakistan, and sustainability is yet to reach the initial and introductory phases (Habib et al., 2021; Hinduja et al., 2023).

In an international context, there are different studies carried out regarding sustainability. Ferguson et al. (2021) used a perspective of teachers about sustainable development in the educational context. Teachers showed less participation in sustainable development by citizenship. Scharenberg et al. (2021) have carried out a similar study. This study analysed ESD implementation from the teachers' perspective concerning their views on ESD. It was longitudinal research that was done between 2007 and 2019. In 2019, the view of the teachers was higher compared to the year 2007. Furthermore, the teachers felt that there was no need for abstract policies; rather, the teaching and acquisition of the objectives of the school should be supported concretely. Nguyen et al. (2020) conducted another study on the topic of ESD in the Vietnam context, and the viewpoints of teachers of geography were explored. The study findings delved into the fact that the perceptions of teachers towards ESD were not like ESD dimensions as espoused by UNESCO. Moreover, sustainable development in higher education has been explored in different studies (Acosta Castellanos & Queiruga-Dios, 2022; Dawe et al., 2005; Svanström et al., 2008)

Literature has consistently shown that faster progress is made when governments and universities consider ESD as a priority and allocate sufficient resources. On the other hand, when sustainability is secondary to institutional concerns, the implementation process is slow regardless of the policy expression. It is the fact that makes it important to note that Pakistan should no longer have a disconnected approach to awareness but an institutionalized approach to ESD.

Research Methodology

It was qualitative research with the research design of phenomenology. This research design was used to understand the lived experiences of participants in their contexts (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Ten faculty members were selected using a purposive sampling technique from a public university in Punjab. This sampling technique was the most suitable for use in qualitative studies to explore participants' perspectives for an in-depth understanding of a complex phenomenon (Patton, 2014). The study participants were selected based on their teaching responsibilities, role in curriculum development, and engagement in projects related to sustainability. To collect data, semi-structured interviews were conducted that lasted 30-40 minutes. Data were analyzed through thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Results of the Study

The following five broad themes were derived from the semi-structured interviews.

Theme 1: Diverse theoretical understandings of ESD

The faculty members expressed various and at times narrow ideas of ESD. The participants saw it in a limited way as protecting the environment, and as having expanded social, cultural, and ethical aspects. One of the participants (P-5) mentioned "ESD has not yet acquired a new meaning in many teachers' minds; it is merely environmental awareness, which involves discussing pollution or planting trees. Sustainability, however, is quite broad; it encompasses social justice, equality, and responsible citizenship."

Another faculty member narrated as "What I discovered after I attended a workshop is that ESD is not a course; it is a philosophy and method of teaching. It must affect the way we teach lessons, deal with students and even the resources." (P-8).

This difference in interpretation aligns with broader trends reported in the literature. This is because many university teachers have a basic understanding of sustainable development, and in most cases, they do not realize that sustainable development extends beyond environmental issues. Without mutual in-depth knowledge of the holistic nature of ESD, including its social, economic, and environmental aspects, faculty participation may be unequal, preventing the infusion of sustainability into teaching practices.

Theme 2: Divided Curriculum Integration

The participants indicated that the content of sustainability is not uniformly integrated into programs, with most ESD activities being disciplined specifically. One of the faculty members (P-3) said,

The syllabus does not directly discuss sustainability, but where feasible, I attempt to incorporate small sections of it. Specifically, in my course, I discuss ethical production and social responsibility. These attempts are positive but not systematic, and students generally have a positive view of them.

Another interviewee (P-10) said in the following words:

Sustainability is discussed in only environmental science courses at our university." It is rarely mentioned in other departments and there is no inter-departmental coordination. Students who reveal interest often do not have frequent opportunities to explore it, even when they are genuinely interested.

This disintegration is consistent with evidence that sustainability rhetoric is incorporated into university policies, but there is limited action in terms of curricular change. Most degree programs do not incorporate much ESD material, so students are exposed to sustainability issues in isolated situations rather than in systematic sections of their curriculum.

Theme 3: Institutional and Structural Barriers

The faculty members identified several barriers to systematic ESD implementation, including outdated curricula, inadequate governance, and a lack of administrative support. One of the faculty members (P-1) said,

We have policies on paper in our university that refer to sustainability, but they are not implemented. There are no specific teams or offices that can see the implementation of this initiative. Due to limited funding, these initiatives have been constrained. For the majority of activities, only voluntary participation is performed by faculty members and students.

Another participant (P-9) narrated his perspective as follows:

The students want participation in different projects related to social or environmental, but due to no long-term plan, mentorship, and disconnection from the coursework, it is not possible. Even if any new project is started, there are hurdles to the administration. This can be improved through university investments in small labs and clubs related to sustainability.

Theme 4: Favourable Perceptions and New Motivation

The study participants showed great enthusiasm for sustainability learning as a transformative potential. One participant (P3) described the following:

Sustainability education may enhance social and meaningful learning for university students. Whenever I provide examples of community well-being, students become more engaged in class. Through this, students not only achieve academic achievement through good scores but also achieve aspirations.

One of the participants (P-7) said that their students enjoyed participation in plantation drives and clear campus campaigns. These activities offers students opportunities to apply their conceptual understanding in practical scenarios.

Theme 5: Requirement of Capacity Building and Cooperation

Faculty members of the university stated the importance of faculty development, coordination, and leadership involvement to achieve effective integration regarding Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). One of the participants (P-5) stated,

Teachers are willing to teach sustainability. Furthermore, knowledge about effective integration into curriculum is absent. Experts should organize regular workshops to display alignment of courses with sustainable development goals. Also, there should be inter-departmental collaborations to exchange resources and ideas.

It was proposed by another participant of the study (P-9) that joint training sessions should be implemented for teachers and students to obtain important benefits from such experiences. This would enable us to appreciate sustainability as practiced rather than as a theory. Universities are encouraged to collaborate with local communities to develop their experiences.

Such requests for capacity building are in line with international directions. The ESD of the UNESCO 2030 roadmap focuses on building educator competencies, youth empowerment, and whole-institution solutions as key areas of action. Studies conducted in the context of developing countries demonstrate that the willingness of university leadership to adopt sustainable practices in terms of professional development and incentives triggers the process of curriculum change and cultural transformation towards ESD (Mulà et al., 2017; Price et al., 2021; Verhulst & Lambrechts, 2015).

Discussion

The results indicate that the situation regarding ESD in public universities in Punjab, Pakistan, is rather complex, with both gaps and opportunities. Faculty knowledge about ESD is quite inconsistent, as those who perceive it with a limited scope and those who view it holistically are few. The experience of the participants shows that ESD is not an extensive part of the curriculum or pedagogy; it is mentioned in individual disciplines or occasionally in seminars. Previous studies support this finding (Habib et al., 2021; Kalsoom et al., 2018; Saqib et al., 2020). A significant knowledge gap exists at the institutional level. Although the concept of sustainability has infiltrated university discourse in the form of vision statements and policies, it is unevenly implemented at both academic and operational levels. Existing initiatives are mostly unplanned and isolated, relying on personal advocates rather than a well-coordinated approach.

There are numerous institutional obstacles to the systematic adoption of ESD: outdated, inflexible curricula; a limited number of educators with capacity and willingness; institutional inertia; poor governance; and the absence of external support and incentives. Such issues are linked and, without funding, it is impossible to implement changes in the curriculum. Without trained educators, new courses cannot be delivered efficiently, and without leadership engagement, programs tend to enter circles. Same studies have been present in the earlier literature (Agbabiaka & Albert, 2025; Ogu & Godspower-Chike, 2025)

However, faculty members also have a high level of intrinsic motivation. Teachers find it important to make the teaching more relevant to its sustainability links, and students are willing to engage in the environmental and social programs provided. This merging of goodwill, connected with top-level policy support and momentum worldwide, provides an opportunity to shift between isolated and systemic work.

Conclusion

It has been shown that the faculty of public sector institutions are at a transitional stage of learning to sustain themselves, as they are building awareness of Education for Sustainable Development but are unable to sustain learning through systematic institutional integration. Although sustainability has emerged in policy discussions and led to individual initiatives, its actual implementation remains quite irregular, with considerable inconsistencies in curriculum design, faculty capacity, governance structures, and resource distribution. The results indicate that to make ESD integration meaningful, the approach should be viewed as both a pedagogical innovation and institutional transformation. There is energy and potential capacity among faculty members. It can be initiated with systematic curricula reforms, professional development, supportive leadership and required resources. Being a developing country, Pakistan is facing different challenges like lack of coordination, outdated curricula, insufficient funding and flaws of capacity building. Therefore, solutions of the challenges should be addressed through political dedication and institutional investment to play a meaningful role towards sustainable development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

Priority for sustainability should be focused as the central vision of the institution through comprehensive education for sustainable development policies, faculty, and external experts' input.

A systematic revision of the curriculum is needed to incorporate sustainability issues and competencies into courses.

For professional development of the faculty, resource allocation is necessary. It can be done through the organization of regular training, seminars, and workshops on ESD concepts, innovative pedagogical practices, and curriculum design.

There should be used to include living laboratories with students' engagement in designing and implementing projects in university premises.

Faculty should be encouraged to collaborate on joint courses and research initiatives.

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